

MART – Mobile Assessment Research Tool

A data collection app combining survey, experience sampling, logging, and data donation

Survey

- Different **input types** (radio, sliders, text, file upload ...)
- **Timed** items
- **HTML** formatting

Mobile Experience Sampling (MESM)

- **Multiple short surveys** a day
- Customizable **notifications**
- Semi-random **scheduling**

Logging (Android)

- Accesses **raw usage event logs** stored by **Android** itself
- Participants need to **grant access** once
- **Regular** access possible

Data Donation

- **Shows instructions** for donations (e.g., **Screen Time**)
- **Screenshot/video upload** or **manual entry**
- Available for **iOS** and **Android**

Paper

Source code

Next step

- **Web interface**
- **Secure**
- **Open-access**
- **Free and simple**

Contact

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